

Examining the effect of teacher's self-efficacy on job satisfaction

Damianus Abun^{(a)*} Eldefonso B. Natividad^(b) Marlene T. Nicolas^(c)
 Theogenia Magallanes^(d) Jecel M. Mansueto^(e)

^(a) Ph.D., Professor, School of Business, Divine Word College of Laoag, Ilocos Norte, Philippines

^(b) Ph.D., Professor, School of Arts, Sciences and Education, Divine Word College of Laoag, Ilocos Norte, Philippines

^(c) Ph.D., Dean, School of Arts, Sciences and Education, Divine Word College of Laoag, Ilocos Norte, Philippines

^(d) EdD, President, School of Religious Education, Saint Benedict College of Northern Luzon, Ilocos Sur, Philippines

^(e) MAEd, Professor, School of Religious Education, Saint Benedict College of Northern Luzon, Ilocos Sur, Philippines

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ABSTRACT

The paper aims to examine the effect of teachers' self-efficacy on job satisfaction. To deepen the study, literature was reviewed and theories were established. The study used the descriptive correlational research design. The total enumeration was the sampling design of the study. It used questionnaires to gather the data. The study found that the teachers' self-efficacy is very high along the three dimensions of teachers' self-efficacy which include self-efficacy in student engagement, instructional strategies, and classroom management. While teachers' job satisfaction was considered high, not very high along the two dimensions such as satisfaction with the work itself and personal growth and career development. Concerning the correlation, it was found that there is a significant correlation between teachers' self-efficacy and job satisfaction.

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Introduction

Measuring quality in the manufacturing company may not be far different from measuring quality in educational service. Though the quality may be defined differently from the manufacturer's view and customer's view, however, both will agree that quality product/service is about the performance of a product that meets the need of the customer. Producing a quality product is a challenge on the part of a manufacturing company or educational institution. It is through offering quality products the company/the institution can profit and survive. Therefore, the school must define and determine the standards of quality and ensure that factors that contribute to the quality product/service must be given serious attention. Quality is not just about a final product or output but it involves three processes and they are input – process – output. Quality output is a result of quality input and process. Thus, planning to produce quality, the management must ensure that the inputs are following the standards required for quality, and the same with the process. Both are equally important to produce quality output. It is certain that even though the inputs such as raw materials, the facilities, and the workers are all following the standards of quality, however, if the process is not defined and not being followed, then the quality result will be affected. The same case with educational institutions. The management must ensure that the inputs such as teachers, students, facilities and well-designed curriculum is following quality standards and methods or process of delivering the lesson to the students also follow the quality standards that have been defined by the institution.

* Corresponding author. ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9693-1541

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One of the critical inputs of the education institution to produce quality education is the teacher. The Oxford Business Group (2017) pointed out two main problems related to raising quality education in the Philippines which are teachers' knowledge and insufficient professional development. Therefore, the ongoing concern of the management is to equip teachers with sufficient knowledge and provide professional development. In line with such concern, management must ensure that teachers who are teaching must fulfill the requirement for a teacher such as educational qualification, specialization, license, experience, research publication, etc. Those are minimum requirements to be a teacher which need to be enhanced continuously. It is important to note that given these minimum requirements have been met, however, teaching self-efficacy does not necessarily follow. Teaching self-efficacy cannot be simply measured by those external requirements because it is a social psychological issue and is part of social cognitive theory. Bandura (1994) defines self-efficacy as one's belief in his/her capability to perform a task and achieve the outcome. Self-efficacy affects how a person feels, thinks, motivates, and behaves and it enhances personal accomplishment and personal well-being. The sources of self-efficacy are mastery experience, vicarious experience, verbal persuasion, and physiological cues (Bandura, 1977).

Finding out the level of self-efficacy of teachers and sources of teachers' self-efficacy is an important step to determine the problems. Some teachers may perform better than others, however, it does not suggest that those who are teaching well are better than the others because the problem might be in the personal and environmental factors. Therefore, by knowing their self-efficacy, the management would know what the problems are, and solving those problems that are not supportive for self-efficacy to grow is an immediate concern of management. Enhancing teachers' self-efficacy is important to improve their motivation to teach and consequently improve their teaching performance.

It has been pointed out that self-efficacy affects how people feel, think and behave (Bandura, 1994). In the same way, we argue that self-efficacy affects job satisfaction. Therefore, solving job dissatisfaction means improving the self-efficacy of teachers. It is noted that teachers are leaving the institution after only a few years of teaching when they are not satisfied with their job. The question is: Is it because they are not satisfied with their teaching job or they do not have the self-efficacy to continue to teach? This is the concern of management to find out. The institution has been experiencing difficulties in retaining the faculty to stay permanently with the institution. There may be other factors that cause the departure of faculty but certainly, the two factors are included which are self-efficacy and job satisfaction. Some faculty left because they are not satisfied and some faculty left because they cannot teach. However, the current concern of investigation is to find out if self-efficacy causes satisfaction or dissatisfaction.

The objective of the study is to provide information for the management and HRD to find ways how to help the faculty improve their self-efficacy which consequently improves their job satisfaction. There have been no studies yet conducted on a similar topic with the Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region. The study is divided into several parts: the first, the introduction which explains the rationale and objective of the study. The second is the literature review that investigates existing literature and studies concerning the current topic. The purpose is to establish the theories of the study. The third is the research methodology which presents the research design, population, locale, instruments, procedures, and statistical treatment of data. The fourth is data presentation and analysis that presents data that were gathered through questionnaires and followed by their analysis. Fifth is the result and discussion and conclusion. This part discusses further the implication of research and its contribution to the existing discussion on the topic.

The study aims to find out the effect of teacher self-efficacy on the job satisfaction of teachers. Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions:

- i. What is the teacher self-efficacy in terms of
 - a. Efficacy in student engagement
 - b. Efficacy in instructional strategies
 - c. Efficacy in classroom management
- ii. What is the job satisfaction of teachers in terms of
 - a. The work itself
 - b. Personal growth and career development
- iii. Is there a relationship between teacher self-efficacy and job satisfaction?

The study assumes that teacher self-efficacy affects behavior and job satisfaction and both variables can be measured.

Review of Literature

This part reviews the existing literature that has discussed the current topic and studies that have been done related to the current investigation. This is to strengthen the theory of the study and to find out what other researchers have found and have not found and therefore helping the current study to fill the gap. The presentation of the literature review is arranged thematically.

Theoretical and Conceptual Framework

The self-efficacy Theory

There are times that we encounter challenges and during those times, we are challenged to face them and take them up or give up. Some people are inspired by challenges and they rise to take the challenges but some people are not motivated to take the challenges and give up. These two groups of people explain the theory of self-efficacy. Those who are inspired by challenges and take up the

challenges are those who have high self-efficacy and those who are not inspired by challenges and give up are those who have low self-efficacy belief. Self-efficacy can explain why some people are successful in performing difficult tasks and some people are not successful. It also explains why some people get stressed easily when facing problems and some are not, why some people are motivated and some are demotivated. Bandura (1997) defines self-efficacy as a person's belief in his/her capacity to succeed in a particular situation. According to him, it is a determinant factor that affects how people feel, think and behave. In other words, it is what one believes he can do in a particular situation or what one is capable of doing (Maddux, 2013).

The self-efficacy theory was coined by a Canadian-American psychologist, a professor at Stanford University, Albert Bandura (1977). He was the first one who introduced the concept before another psychologist such as Kathy Kolbe (2009) who also discussed the concept. Bandura (1977) defined self-efficacy as "a person's particular set of beliefs that determine how well one can execute a plan of action in prospective situations" (Bandura, 1977). Kolbe (2009) contended that self-efficacy is a determining factor in measuring cognitive strength, determination, and perseverance to overcome obstacles and achieve goals. It provides the foundation for motivation, well-being, and personal accomplishment (Lopez-Garrido, 2020) and it enables the person to handle stress, anxiety, adversities, and achieve performance (Lopez-Garrido, 2020). This theory argued that one of the influential factors for success is self-efficacy. It explains the reason why many people can still perform and achieve successful performance even during a crisis. They can adjust their lives during difficult times and can make effective decisions (Maddux, 1995). Thus, it is crucial to enhance an individual's perception of his/her capabilities to produce positive outcomes (Gallagher, 2012). Lack of self-efficacy can affect well-being and reduce performance which leads to failure.

After Bandura (1977) published his seminal work, since then, there have been many studies conducted by many psychologists concerning the effect of self-efficacy toward job performance, job satisfaction, and well-being. The reason why many psychologists investigate such a topic is because of its impact on psychological well-being, behavior, and motivation (Bandura, 1977 as cited by Cherry, 2020). For example, Bandura and Adams (1977) have conducted a study on the effect of self-efficacy on behavioral change. According to the result of the study, self-efficacy is found to be a highly accurate and superior predictor for behavioral change. This is evidenced by the result of the study of Bandura (2001) himself on the effect of self-efficacy and job outcome who found that high-level self-efficacy promotes attitude and behavior which contribute to a positive outcome and job satisfaction. This result is also confirmed by a later study by Lai and Chen (2012) on the effect of self-efficacy on job satisfaction and performance. The study found a correlation between self-efficacy and job satisfaction and performance. A similar result was found in the study of Borgogni, et.al (2013), on the role of the effect of self-efficacy on job satisfaction and absences. The study confirms the finding of other studies that self-efficacy affects job satisfaction and absences. Demir (2018) forward the similar finding that self-efficacy affects job satisfaction, organizational commitment, motivation, and job involvement. The same finding was found across other jobs such as teaching. The study of Türkoğlu, et.al (2017) found the effect of teachers' self-efficacy and job satisfaction which suggests that self-efficacy is a significant predictor for teachers' job satisfaction.

Self-efficacy is not innate in a person but is the result of opportunity, social environment, and personal factors. It is a result of opportunity because when a person has been allowed to perform a certain job and successfully perform the job, such mastery experience will promote self-confidence in the person. Besides mastery experience, self-efficacy is also supported by the social environment in which a person lives and performed the task. One can get self-efficacy by seeing someone performs a certain task successfully which later motivates the person to believe in himself that she/he can do it. Self-efficacy can also be a result of verbal persuasion coming from friends or family or higher-ups. Recognition and praises coming from them boost self-efficacy in the person. However, given those elements are present but without emotional and physical fitness to perform the task may affect self-efficacy. For example, when someone experiences distress and physical injury may affect the self-confidence of the person to perform the task. Thus, along with this concept, Bandura (1977) summarized the sources of self-efficacy which are mastery experience, vicarious experience, verbal persuasion, and emotional, psychological, and physical cues. Maddux (2013) added the fifth source of self-efficacy which is an imaginal experience that explains self-efficacy can be a result of visualizing one's self perform successfully in a particular situation.

Teachers' Self-efficacy and its dimensions.

Teachers have been playing a very significant role in the academic achievement of students. This is one of the objectives of every teacher. However, achieving such an objective may not be easy without self-efficacy which according to Bandura (1997), is important on how this objective can be achieved. Cognitive self-assessment on one's capability is important to motivate a person to go for a certain activity or not. According to Bandura (1997) person who has high self-efficacy develops an interest in the activity, a sense of commitment, and can handle setbacks and challenges. Following such a concept, having high self-efficacy will affect the way how teachers are conducting their classes.

Teaching is not only about delivering the content effectively but to deliver the content effectively, different elements are involved such as instructional strategies, classroom management, student engagement (Tschannen-Moran & Woolfolk, 2001). Thus, teachers' self-efficacy in instructional strategies, classroom management, and student engagement are important elements to achieve the instructional objective. Teachers should believe in themselves that they can handle their tasks, obligations, and problems effectively (Barni, et.al, 2019) and this is the concern of self-efficacy. This concept refers to the definition of Bandura (1977, 1986, 1997) about self-efficacy. Bandura defined self-efficacy as "an individual belief in his/her capability to execute behaviors necessary to produce

specific performance outcome". In a similar vein, Skaalvik and Skaalvik (2007) define teacher self-efficacy as "individual teachers' beliefs in their capabilities to plan, organize and carry out activities to attain given educational goals". Bandura argued that self-efficacy may help develop one's motivation, behavior and influence different aspects of human experience including the eagerness and the energy of the person to achieve the goals. In the same way, we also argue that teachers' self-efficacy can boost their motivation and excitement to perform their teaching job. This is evidenced in the study of Alibakhshi, et.al (2020) about the consequences of teachers' self-efficacy. The result of their study pointed out that teachers' self-efficacy brought some consequences such as teaching practices, learners' motivation, and academic achievement. Thus, it is often said that teachers' self-efficacy is a determinant factor in the teaching behaviors of teachers (Henson, 2001).

The result of researches as cited by Lazarides and Warner (2020) showed that teachers who have a high level of self-efficacy are more open to new teaching methods, set challenging goals, exhibit a greater level of planning and organization, enjoy solving problems, and can adjust their teaching strategies when they encounter problems or difficulties. In the same vein, Bray-Clark and Bates (2003) also found in their study that self-efficacy is correlated to teachers' effectiveness and students' outcome. This finding is consistent with the findings of other studies which were summarized by Zee and Koomen (2016) concerning the effect of teacher efficacy on students' academic adjustment, patterns of teacher behaviors and practices related to classroom quality, factors underlying teachers' psychological well-being, job satisfaction and commitment. Another study also found that teacher self-efficacy affects students' engagement, instruction, and classroom management (Fackler, et.al, (2021).

Measuring teacher self-efficacy in a single construct as done by Schwarzer et al. (1999) may be less useful for the researchers and teacher self-development. Besides, such a single dimension cannot measure the multiple functions teacher perform concerning teaching. It has been emphasized by Skaalvik & Bong, (2003), that self-efficacy is a multidimensional construct. Even Bandura (1997) himself has argued that teacher self-efficacy is a multidimensional construct to measure their main functions. Since teachers have multiple functions, thus Bandura (n.d) proposed seven dimensions of teacher self-efficacy which are influence decision making, influence school resources, instruction, and discipline, enlist parental involvement and create a positive school climate. Reading these dimensions, one immediately knows that these seven dimensions do not reflect the main function of a teacher in the classroom. Knowing such limitations, Tschannen-Moran and Woolfolk (2001) developed a three dimensions scale of teacher self-efficacy which are instructional strategies, classroom management, and students' engagement. Although there is some criticism about these three dimensions, however, these three dimensions have been proven to be reliable through factor analysis and therefore these dimensions have been accepted as reliable dimensions for teacher self-efficacy. The criticism is that teacher self-efficacy is reduced to three dimensions only which may not reflect all the functions of teachers and most of the items lack obstacles which are one factor determining self-efficacy as recommended by Bandura (1997). Taking such criticism in mind, Skaalvik and Skaalvik (2007) developed six dimensions which include instruction, adapting education to individual students' needs, motivating students, keeping disciplines, cooperating with colleagues and parents, and coping with changes and challenges.

For our study, the current study cannot include all the dimensions proposed by Bandura (n.d) with his seven dimensions and Skaalvik and Skaalvik (2007) with their six dimensions. The current study adopts the three dimensions of Tschannen-Moran and Woolfolk (2007) which are instructional strategies, classroom management, and student engagement. The current researcher takes these three dimensions because these three dimensions are closely related to the main function of teachers in the classroom daily.

Job Satisfaction and its Dimensions

Job satisfaction of employees has been a serious concern of management because of its impact on employees' performance and productivity. The idea of job satisfaction was brought to light by Hoppock (1935) as he defined it as "any combination of psychological, physiological and environmental circumstances that cause and person truthfully to say "I am satisfied with my job". He refers to job satisfaction as feeling toward a job and such satisfaction is caused by psychological, physiological, and environmental elements of the job. It means that when the job does not overburden the person physically and psychologically and when the work environment is conducive to work, then it contributes to job satisfaction. This concept has led researchers to define job satisfaction as "the employees' perception and feeling about the work environment" (Munir & Rahman, 2016). Such definition is considered broad because it refers to many different factors of the work environment such as pay (Shaw, et.al, 1998), career promotion (Labov, 1997), benefits (Alexander, Bloom & Nuchols, 1994), relationship, reciprocal, and engagement (Cappelli, 1992). Thus, other researchers tried to simplify the definition only limited to the attitude which involves cognitive aspect, affective and conative aspects. Thus, Spector (1977, 1997) defined it as "how people feel about their jobs and different aspects of their jobs". This definition refers to job satisfaction as the extent of feeling toward the job in terms of like or dislike to the job. However, Brief (1998) does not limit the definition of satisfaction only with feelings but includes "thoughts" (cognitive) as he defines job satisfaction as "one's feelings and thoughts towards jobs that expressed effectively or cognitively to some degree of favor or disfavor experience". Following his definition, job satisfaction, therefore job satisfaction represents the emotion, feelings, and thoughts of employees toward the job. The definition of Brief (1998) sees job satisfaction as a result of an attitude toward the work. It is a result of the cognitive and affective attitude of employees toward the job, whether it is positive or negative. Satisfaction is the consequence of a positive attitude toward the work. Thus, in line with such definition, Vroom (1964) viewed job satisfaction as a positive attitude and behavior (conative) toward work that influences the employees to commit to their work.

Job satisfaction is an important element of the job that management has to manage because failure to identify the causes of dissatisfaction may affect the organization negatively. Because of its serious consequences to the organization, many researchers have been devoting their time to investigating job satisfaction and finding out the effect of job satisfaction on performance and those studies have found a positive correlation between the two variables. Take examples of Siengthai and Pila-Ngarm (2016), Ali and Farooqi (2014), Al-Ali, et.al (2019), Fadlallh (2015), Helmi, and Abunar (2021), and Bakan, et.al. (2014). The result of their studies confirmed the positive relationship between job satisfaction and performance. There can be a lot of factors affecting job satisfaction such as work and life balance, isolation and belonging, flexibility, resource efficiency, trust and respect (Willis, 2016), amount of work, workload, training, environmental conditions, work independence, promotion possibilities, relationship with supervisor, stability and job security (Parada, 2018), the compensation system, job characteristics, working conditions, leadership style, promotion opportunities, and co-workers (Smith et al. 1969). Trying to improve job satisfaction of employees and performance means that the management needs to give attention to all those details.

Since job satisfaction is caused by many different factors, thus job satisfaction is not a single construct but is a multidimensional construct. As a result, this leads to many researchers investigating dimensions of job satisfaction. Munir and Rahman (2015) identified five dimensions of job satisfaction which are the nature of work, salary, managerial support, promotion, and co-worker support. According to the researchers, these are the factors that cause satisfaction and dissatisfaction which may lead to loyalty to the company or abandonment. When employees are satisfied with the work itself, salary, support, and promotion, they would stay and if not, they would leave. While Rutherford, et.al (2009) have identified seven dimensions of job satisfaction namely satisfaction with the supervision, satisfaction with the overall job, satisfaction with policy and support, satisfaction with promotion and advancement, satisfaction with pay, satisfaction with coworkers, and satisfaction with customers. In a similar vein, Lee, et.al (2017) identified five dimensions of job satisfaction that may not be far different from the dimensions identified by other researchers such as salary and welfare, work itself, leader behavior, personal growth, and interpersonal relationship. Similar to these dimensions, Özpehlivan and Acar (2015) identified six dimensions of job satisfaction such as management skills, co-workers, job and working conditions, promotion, pay, and external environment. AliAbadi, et.al (2014) mention five dimensions of job satisfaction and these are salary, supervision, reward, coworkers, and communication. Garcia-Almeida, et.al (2014) named five dimensions of job satisfaction such as job conditions, reward system, relations with superiors, relations with coworkers, and organizational policies.

Based on the dimensions identified above by different researchers and considering the purpose of this paper to investigate the effect of self-efficacy of teachers and job satisfaction, therefore, the paper adopts two main dimensions of job satisfaction which are the satisfaction with the work itself and personal growth and career development. These dimensions have been consistently found in the work of Munir and Rahman (2015), Rutherford, et.al (2009), Lee, et.al (2017), Özpehlivan and Acar (2015), Garcia-Almeida, et.al (2014) and Abun, et.al (2021). These dimensions have been tested and used in several studies and therefore considered to be reliable as dimensions of job satisfaction.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1: The conceptual framework depicts the correlation between the independent and dependent variables in which teacher self-efficacy affects job satisfaction; *Source:* Tschannen-Moran & Woolfolk (2001); Abun, et.al (2021).

Hypothesis

Studies have found that occupational self-efficacy/self-efficacy affects work performance (Cetin & Askun, 2018, Randhawa, 2004, Na-Nan & Sanamthong, 2019). Based on these findings, the current study hypothesizes that teacher self-efficacy correlates to job satisfaction.

The Scope and Delimitation of the Study

The study is conducted in the Divine Word College of Laoag which is located in Ilocos Norte, Philippines and it limits its investigation only on three dimensions of teacher self-efficacy such as efficacy in student engagement, classroom management, and instructional strategies and job satisfaction along with two dimensions such as the work itself and personal growth and career development.

Research & Methodology

As a scientific investigation, it requires following research methodology and design. The research design of the study is descriptive assessment and correlational research design. As pointed out by Ariola (2006) that a descriptive correlation study is intended to

describe the relationship among variables without seeking to establish a causal connection. While descriptive research is simply to describe a population, a situation, or a phenomenon. It is also used to describe profiles, frequency distribution, describe characteristics of people, situations, or phenomena. In short, it answers the question of what, when, how, where, and not why question (McCombes, 2020).

The locale of the Study

The locale of the study was Divine Word College of Laoag. This college is located in Laoag City, the capital of Ilocos Norte.

Population

The respondents of the study are the teachers of the Divine Word College of Laoag. Since the number of teachers is limited, therefore, the total enumeration sampling was used and thus all faculty were taken as respondents of the study.

Data Gathering instruments

The current study adopted the short-form questionnaires of Tschannen-Moran & Woolfolk (2001) on teacher self-efficacy which is known as the Ohio State Teacher Efficacy Scale or Teachers’ Sense Efficacy Scale and the questionnaires of Abun, et.al (2021) for job satisfaction.

Data Gathering Procedures

To preserve the integrity of scientific research, the data were gathered after the approval of the President of the college. The researcher sent a letter to the president and after the letter was approved, the questionnaires were distributed by the researcher's representative. Then the researcher's representative from the institution collected the data and submitted it to the researcher for tabulation.

Ethical Procedures

The study was carried out after the research ethics committee examined and approved the content of the paper if it does not violate ethical standards and if it does not cause harm to human life and the environment.

Statistical Treatment of Data

To analyze the data, descriptive and inferential statistic was used. The weighted mean was used to determine the level of teacher self-efficacy and job satisfaction. While Pearson r was used to measure the correlation between teacher self-efficacy and teachers’ job satisfaction. The following ranges of values with their descriptive interpretation were used:

<i>Statistical Range</i>	<i>Descriptive Interpretation</i>
4.21-5.00	<i>strongly agree/ Very High</i>
3.41-4.20	<i>Agree/High</i>
2.61-3.40	<i>moderately agree</i>
1.81-2.60	<i>Disagree/Low</i>
1.00-1.80	<i>Strongly disagree/Very Low</i>

Data Presentation and Analysis

As required by scientific study, it must follow prescribed research methodology and be supported by data. Thus, this part presents data that was gathered through research instruments or research questionnaires that were tabulated statistically. The data presentation follows the arrangement of the research problems.

Problem 1: What is the teacher self-efficacy in terms of (i) Efficacy in student engagement, (ii) Efficacy in instructional strategies, (iii) efficacy in classroom management

Table 1: Self-Efficacy in Student Engagement

No	Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1	How much can you do to motivate students who show low interest in school work?	4.39	SA/VH
2	How much can you do to get students to believe they can do well in schoolwork?	4.46	SA/VH
3	How much can you do to help students value learning?	4.46	SA/VH
4	How much can you assist families in helping their children do well in school?	4.36	SA/VH
Composite Mean		4.42	SA/VH

Source: Tschannen-Moran & Woolfolk (2001)

Based on the data presented in the table, it reveals that as a whole, the self-efficacy of teachers in terms of self-efficacy in student engagement obtained a composite mean of 4.42 which is described as "strongly agree/very high". This composite mean rating

suggests that as a whole the self-efficacy of teachers in terms of self-efficacy in student engagement is not high and it is not very low, low, or moderate but it is very high. It means that teachers of the Divine Word College of Laoag have very high self-efficacy. This indicates that teachers can motivate students to show interest in their school work, to believe in themselves that they can do well in school work, help motivate students to value learning, and assist students' families to help their children do well in school work.

Table 2: Efficacy in Instructional Strategies.

No	Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1	To what extent can you craft good questions for your students?	4.28	SA/VH
2	How much can you use a variety of assessment strategies?	4.23	SA/VH
3	To what extent can you provide an alternative explanation or example when students are confused?	4.32	SA/VH
4	How well can you implement alternative strategies in your classroom?	4.33	SA/VH
Composite Mean		4.29	SA/VH

Source: Tschannen-Moran & Woolfolk (2001)

As shown by the data on the table, it appears that as a whole, the teachers' self-efficacy in terms of efficacy in instructional strategies obtained a composite mean of 4.29 which is considered as "strongly agree/very high". This rating indicates that as a whole the self-efficacy of teachers of the Divine Word College of Laoag in terms of efficacy in instructional strategies is not high and it is also not very low, low, or moderate but it is very high. As whole teachers strongly agree that they can craft good questions for their students, use a variety of assessment strategies, provide alternative explanations or examples when students get confused and can implement alternative strategies in the classroom.

Table 3: Self-Efficacy in Classroom Management

No	Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1	How much can you do to control disruptive behavior in the classroom?	4.33	SA/VH
2	How much can you do to get children to follow classroom rules?	4.35	SA/VH
3	How much can you do to calm a student who is disruptive or noisy?	4.27	SA/VH
4	How well can you establish a classroom management system with each group of students?	4.27	SA/VH
Composite Mean		4.30	SA/VH

Source: Tschannen-Moran & Woolfolk (2001)

In terms of classroom management, the data on the table manifests that as a whole the self-efficacy of teachers of the Divine Word College of Laoag in terms of self-efficacy in classroom management got a composite mean of 4.30 which is understood as "strongly agree/very high". Such composite mean rating implies that as a whole teachers' self-efficacy in terms of classroom management is not high, and it is not also very low, low, or moderate but it is very high. This rating confirms that teachers of the Divine Word College of Laoag can control disruptive behavior in the classroom, can get students to follow classroom rules, and can calm the students who are making noise, and can establish a classroom management system with each group of students.

Table 4: Summary table

No.	Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1	Efficacy in Student engagement	4.42	SA/VH
2	Efficacy in Instructional strategies	4.29	SA/VH
3	Efficacy in classroom management	4.30	SA/VH
Overall Mean		4.34	SA/VH

In summary, based on the data provided in the table, it reveals that overall teachers' self-efficacy in terms of efficacy in student engagement, instructional strategies, and classroom management obtain an overall mean rating of 4.34 which is described as strongly agree or very high. This overall mean rating concludes that teachers have very high self-efficacy in engaging the students in the classroom and can apply different instructional strategies and manage the classroom.

Problem 2: What is the job satisfaction of teachers in terms of (i) The work itself and(ii) personal growth and career development

Table 5: The Work Itself

No	Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1	I am interested in my work and the work is suitable for my background.	4.25	SA/VH
2	The work improves my skills and knowledge	4.33	SA/VH
3	I can do the best for my work	4.38	SA/VH
4	Through the work, I can realize my aspirations	4.31	SA/VH
5	I have been provided with the required information to perform my work	4.20	A/H
6	The management encourages self-thinking while at work	4.05	A/H
7	The work matches my experience, skills, and my physical ability	4.21	SA/VH
8	The management gives importance to my ideas to do my work better.	4.08	A/H
9	Updates employees with new information about the organization	3.89	A/H
10	The management respects my efforts and my initiatives	3.84	A/H
Composite Mean		4.15	A/H

Source: Abun, et.al (2021).

As indicated by the data on the table, it shows that as a whole, the job satisfaction of teachers in terms of satisfaction with the work itself obtained a composite mean of 4.15 which is described as "agree/high". This rating suggests that as a whole teachers' job satisfaction in terms of satisfaction with the work itself is not very high and it is also not very low, low, or moderate but it is high. This rating indicates that as a whole, the teachers agree that they are interested in the work because it is suitable with their educational background, and the work improves their skills and knowledge. Because of their interest, knowledge, and skills, they can do the best for their work and can realize their aspirations through their work. Beyond that, they also agree that they have been provided with the necessary information to perform their work, and management encourages self-thinking while at work. Besides, the work matches their experience, skills, and physical ability and gives importance to individual ideas on how to perform their work, and updates teachers with the information about the organization and the management respect individual efforts and initiatives.

Table 6: Personal growth and career development

No	Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1	There is the availability of schemes for personal growth and development	3.78	A/H
2	There is communication provided for the employees related to policies on personal growth and development.	3.55	A/H
3	There are activities or programs provided for personal growth and development	3.57	A/H
4	There is a rotation of work or job to learn new skills.	3.60	A/H
5	The management provides seminars and workshops for employees' development	3.53	A/H
6	There is employee involvement in the decision-making process	3.42	A/H
7	Opportunities provided for feedbacks and counseling facilities	3.44	A/H
8	There is an interest shown by the management in the development and growth of their subordinates.	3.36	SWA/M
Composite Mean		3.53	A/H

Source: Abun, et.al (2021)

As pointed out by the data on the table, it displays that as a whole, the job satisfaction of teachers of the Divine Word College of Laoag in terms of personal growth and career development received a composite mean rating of 3.53 which is considered as "agree/high". This composite mean rating suggests that as a whole teachers' job satisfaction in terms of personal growth and career development is not very high and it is also not very low, low, or moderate but it is high.

These results denote that as whole teachers are highly satisfied with their personal growth and career development because there is the availability of schemes for personal growth and development, communications provided for the employees/teachers related to personal growth and development, activities or programs provided for personal growth and development, rotation of work or job to learn new skills, employee involvement in the decision-making process, opportunities provided for feedbacks and counseling facilities, the interest shown by the management in the development and growth of their subordinates and the management provides seminars and workshops for employees' development.

Table 7: Summary table

No	Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1	The Work itself	4.15	A/H
2	Personal growth and career development	3.53	A/H
	Overall Mean	3.84	A/H

The summary table demonstrates that overall, the job satisfaction of teachers of the Divine Word College of Laoag in terms of the work itself and personal growth and career development obtained an overall mean rating of 3.84 which is described as "agree/high". This rating indicates that overall teachers highly agree that they are satisfied with their work and their personal growth and career development.

Problem 3: Is there a relationship between teacher self-efficacy and job satisfaction?

Table 8: Correlation table

Efficacy	Job Satisfaction			
		Work Itself	Personal Growth and Career Development	Overall Job Satisfaction
Efficacy in Student Engagement	Pearson Correlation	.627**	.187	.424**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.053	.000
Efficacy in Instructional Strategies	Pearson Correlation	.662**	.208*	.455**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.031	.000
Efficacy in Classroom Management	Pearson Correlation	.696**	.291**	.526**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.002	.000
Overall Efficacy	Pearson Correlation	.712**	.248**	.505**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.010	.000

**Correlation is significant at the .01 level (2-tailed)

*Correlation is significant at the .0 level (2-tailed)

Based on the Pearson r correlation coefficient table, it demonstrates that overall teachers' self-efficacy is significantly correlated at 0.01 level (2-tailed) and .0 level (2-tailed) with the job satisfaction. Taking it singly, the Pearson r correlation coefficient shows that efficacy in instructional strategies and classroom management are significantly correlated with job satisfaction in terms of the work itself and personal growth and career development. While efficacy in student engagement is significantly correlated with job satisfaction in terms of the work itself but it does not correlate with personal growth and career development.

Result and Analysis

Researches on self-efficacy show that one's success in performing a certain task in a particular situation is not just contributed by the skills and knowledge but it is also contributed by self-efficacy. Believing in one's self is a motivating factor that can help a person to take up a certain task or a job and succeed. Bandura (1977) as cited by Cherry (2020) has pointed out that believing in our ability to succeed plays important role in how we think, act, and how we feel about our place in this world. It affects our belief in our capability to perform a task and achieve a goal (Maddux & Kleiman, 2021). There have been studies pointing out the influence of self-efficacy or self-belief toward the different areas of life such as well-being (Sabouripour, et.al, 2021), job satisfaction (Bargsted, et.al, 2019), work performance, or engagement (Machmud, 2018, Yakin & Erdil, 2012). These studies remind us about how important self-efficacy is. Thus, this must be one area of concern for the management.

The result of the current study confirmed the finding of many findings of different researchers about the influence of self-efficacy on the job satisfaction of teachers. The study found that self-efficacy is important to promote the job satisfaction of teachers. This suggests that the higher the self-efficacy of teachers is in terms of their ability to engage students in the classroom, instructional strategies, and classroom management, the more they are satisfied with their work and their career. Their self-confidence helps them to perform their task and achieve their goal. Thus, this must be one of the key important areas of management to be given serious attention. Providing program development that enhances teachers' self-efficacy would help promote the well-being of teachers and satisfaction with their work. In the case of this study, the management needs to equip teachers with different classroom strategies to engage students in the classroom instruction, and different instructional strategies and classroom management. The more they are equipped along these dimensions, the higher their self-efficacy becomes.

Conclusions

This study aimed to measure the effect of teachers' self-efficacy on job satisfaction. There were three dimensions of teachers' self-efficacy explored which include self-efficacy in student engagement, instructional strategies, and classroom management. In terms of job satisfaction, two elements were investigated which are satisfied with the work itself and personal growth and career development. The results found that as a whole, the teachers of the Divine Word College of Laoag have very high self-efficacy along

the three dimensions. In terms of job satisfaction, it was found that teachers have a high job satisfaction along with the work itself and personal growth, and career development.

Concerning the relationship between teachers' self-efficacy and job satisfaction, the Pearson r correlation coefficient found that there is a significant correlation. The finding suggests that teachers' self-efficacy affects the job satisfaction of teachers. Therefore, the hypothesis of this study is accepted. It is recommended that the management need to provide programs that can enhance the teachers' self-efficacy.

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